

Importance of Shearing Deformation in Dynamical Mechanical Tests for Viscoelastic Properties of Continuous Fiber Thermoplastic Composites

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Abstract

The importance of shearing deformation when utilizing flexural tests to determine the relaxation properties of CF/PEKK [1] composites as a function of temperature is discussed in the context of Timoshenko beam theory with the goal of understanding differences between the 0-degree and 90-degree test results. Relaxation data are presented for relaxation moduli developed with the conventional dynamical mechanical test system. The range in temperature examined was 30 – 350 °C.

1 INTRODUCTION

The use of the three-point bending test to develop quasi-static and viscoelastic stress relaxation properties of polymers is well documented in the literature [2-3]. Furthermore, dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) test facilities required to carry out these experiments as a function of temperature typically utilize property characteristics restricted to isotropic materials when converting imposed flexural deformation or force to determine the flexural stress within the test specimen. Of course, the correct relationship between applied deflection and the resulting stresses in the specimen for both orthotropic and isotropic systems is well known as Timoshenko beam theory [4].

$$\delta_T = \frac{PL^3}{48EI} + \frac{PL}{4k_sGA} \quad (1)$$

Where E and G are the appropriate Young's and shearing moduli of the orthotropic or isotropic medium for the 0-degree test geometry. In the present case, the two test geometries are in the 1-3 plane (0-degree test) and 2-3 plane (90-degree test) planes, where the fiber direction is 1, and the thickness direction is 3. The properties in equation (1) for the 0-degree specimen are thereby, E_{11} and G_{13} . For the 90-degree test, the Young's modulus is E_{22} and the shearing modulus, G_{23} . The other variables in equation (1) are the applied central load, P, the specimen span, L, the beam moment of inertia, I, cross-sectional area, A, and shear correction factor, k_s . Flexural stress calculation as a function of the applied load, P is identical for both beams of isotropic and orthotropic media.

The flexural test is typically used with confidence in prediction of Young's modulus for isotropic materials systems. However, for highly orthotropic materials this approach can produce misleading results, as discussed in reference [3]. Table 1 illustrates the conventional approach in utilizing only the first term of equation (1) to predict Young's modulus for a CF/PEKK composite. As discussed in reference [3], the modulus data developed within the Q800 DMA System of TA Instruments and utilized in the present study can yield moduli data for thin specimens that can be as much as 10-20 Percent in error.

2 APPARENT REDUCTION IN YOUNG'S MODULUS, E_{11}

The E_{11} modulus experimental data for the 0-degree flexure test are shown in Table 1. Furthermore, the data sheet of reference [1] shows the tensile and compressive moduli of the composite to be 139.0 GPa and 127.0 GPa, respectively. Thus, the ambient test results of 126.42 GPa is only 5 percent less than the average of tensile and compressive modulus values reported in reference [1].

Temp. °C	30	120	150	180	210	240	270	300	330
E_{11} , GPa	126.42	130.89	128.27	120.40	115.30	107.55	99.29	80.61	18.05

Table 1 Values of E_{11} determined from deflection, δ and force, P utilizing classical beam theory (only first term in equation (1))

The data in Table 1 imply that the Young's modulus, E_{11} , is reduced from 126.42 GPa at 30 °C to 18.05 GPa at 330 °C. Yet the modulus of carbon fiber does not change over this temperature range and the contribution of the matrix phase to the composite tensile modulus is of second-order. Hence, it must be concluded that utilizing the conventional approach to determine E_{11} temperature dependence of the CF/PEKK composite will not yield the desired results. The following discussion explores the causes for this inconsistency.

3 RELATIVE SHEARING DEFORMATION TO FLEXURAL DEFORMATION

Equation (1) illustrates the relationship between the total beam central deflection, δ_T and that due to both the flexural stress, δ_f and to the shearing stress, δ_s . The constant, k_s is an area correction factor, typically taken as 5/6 for beams of rectangular cross-section. The important message of equation (1) is that both flexural stress and shearing stress contribute to the beam deflection and that their relative contributions can be measured by the ratio of the two terms, as shown in equation (2). Furthermore, the ratio of the Young's modulus to the shearing modulus and the square of the ratio of the beam height to beam span are shown to determine the relative contributions of the two deformation modes.

$$\frac{\delta_s}{\delta_f} = \left(\frac{1}{k_s} \right) \left(\frac{E_{11}}{G_{13}} \right) \left(\frac{h}{L} \right)^2 \quad (2)$$

Equation (2) can be utilized to determine the beam aspect ratio (L/h) that minimizes the influence of shearing deformation upon beam deflection, but its use requires knowledge of both the material

shearing modulus and Young's modulus. For isotropic materials, the shearing modulus and Young's modulus are related by the Poisson's ratio, ν .

$$\frac{\delta_s}{\delta_f} = \frac{12(1+\nu)}{5} \left(\frac{h}{L}\right)^2 \approx 3 \left(\frac{h}{L}\right)^2 \quad (3)$$

Thus, for isotropic materials in bending, the ratio of the shearing to flexural displacements is less than 0.002 for $L/h = 45$, ($\nu = 0.3$). In the present study, the DMA span was set at $L = 50$ mm and for the beam height of 1.08 mm, the ratio was 0.001. This ratio is clearly acceptable for isotropic systems, but this may not be the case for orthotropic materials where the ratio of Young's modulus to shearing modulus can be quite large.

4 FLEXURAL TESTS FOR VISCOELASTIC RELAXATION

Dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) test facilities are often utilized to measure viscoelastic stress relaxation of composite materials such as CF/PEKK. A typical DMA test facility is shown in Figure 1 where the load or displacement control actuator and the pin supports are shown. The beam loading condition in Figure 1 is for three-point bending. The span length shown is 50 mm, but the apparatus can be adjusted for span length of 25 mm, as well.

Figure1. Conventional DMA Test Facility for Three-point Flexure Tests

The DMA test facility allows for control of the time-temperature history of the test sample for harmonic or creep/relaxation loading conditions. Stress relaxation experiments are carried out by imposing a specified deflection at the mid-span of the beam and monitoring the reduction in the applied force with time. For isotropic materials, the relationship between beam deflection and flexural stress, utilizing Euler-Bernoulli beam theory, is well known and is correct for these materials for $L/h \geq 45$. However, as shown in the previous section, this is not true for highly orthotropic materials such as CF/PEKK in the 0-degree test geometry. Thus, issues with the role of shearing deformation in flexural testing under multiple temperature conditions are also present for viscoelastic stress relaxation. Furthermore, the relationship between total beam deflection and force involves both flexural and shearing deformation components in the viscoelastic case, just as it does in quasi-static testing.

The viscoelastic experimental results for the 0-degree composite beam composed of CF/PEKK is shown in Figure 2. The data presented in Figure 2 were determined by the conventional DMA system wherein a constant central displacement of 0.193 mm was imposed and the decay in force with time was recorded as a function of temperature.

Figure 2. Apparent relaxation data for the 0-degree CF/PEKK composite beam in three-point bending

The dilemma presented in the foregoing discussion is that to separate the contributions of flexural and shearing deformations to determine beam total deformation requires knowledge of the very property that the test is designed to determine, namely E_{11} and G_{13} . Thus, a strategy must be

developed to quantify the relative contributions of the two deformation modes over the temperature range of interest. For the 0-degree specimen, test temperature provides the vehicle for this separation because the deformation due to shearing stress shows significant change with temperature, while the deformation due to flexural stress does not. This characteristic of the 0-degree specimen was illustrated earlier through equation (2). In Timoshenko beam theory [4], the two deformation modes are coupled in series and both support the same applied load, P , while contributing individually to the total deflection, δ_T . If the Young's modulus, E_{11} is taken as equal to the value measured at instantaneous, ambient conditions and to be independent of temperature, then deformation due to the flexural normal stress, δ_f can be calculated using Euler-Bernoulli beam theory (first term in equation 1) and subtracted from the total deflection to determine the deflection due to the shearing stress, δ_s .

Test data from the DMA in Figure 3 shows 90-degree modulus relaxation data taken for a CF/PEKK composite subjected to three-point bending of the 90-degree specimen over the temperature range of 40 °C to 300 °C. Hexagonal symmetry at the microscopic scale of the CF/PEKK implies that the 2-3 plane is a plane of transvers isotropy. Thus, the 90-degree flexure specimen satisfies minimization of the shearing contribution to lateral deflection at a specimen length to height ratio of 45. These results show that the relaxation modulus exhibits significant dependence upon temperature, falling from 9034 MPa at 30°C to 273 MPa at 300 °C. Furthermore, significant relaxation in stress occurs in the first minute after application of the applied displacement.

Figure 3 Relaxation of the transverse modulus, E_{22} from 30°C to 300 °C

Given that the polymer matrix relaxation is largely responsible for relaxation of all matrix-dominated properties of the composite, the composite shearing modulus, G_{13} should exhibit quite similar behavior to E_{22} . Thereby, the authors chose to derive the relaxation properties in shear from the 90-degree data by fitting the form of the 90-degree relaxation data to the $t = 0, T = 30^\circ\text{C}$ value for shearing modulus (5297 MPa) reported in the literature [5]. The resulting shearing modulus relaxation data for G_{13} are shown in Figure 4 where the primary relaxation occurs in the first 5 minutes at $T \geq 240^\circ\text{C}$.

Figure 4 Relaxation data for the transverse shearing modulus, G_{13}

5 SHEAR MODULUS RELAXATION

Data for G_{13} presented in Table 2 were derived from the instantaneous values of the shearing modulus as a function of temperature shown in Figure 4. Experimental results and predictions (Equation 1) of the magnitude of the quasi-static, central force, P in three-point bending in the DMA Test system are presented for multiple temperatures and for a fixed displacement of 0.193 mm. The test specimen geometry was $L = 50$ mm, $h = 1.08$ mm and specimen width of 12.48 mm. If the Young's modulus, E_{11} is held constant at 126.42 GPa for the calculations and the shearing modulus is varied from 5297 MPa to 158 MPa, it is informative to examine the predicted force required to sustain the 0.193 mm in deflection as shown in Table 2. The close agreement between predictions and experiments for the magnitude of the force required to produce a deflection of 0.193 mm shows that the dominant contribution to the observed apparent relaxation of E_{11} , is actually due to relaxation of G_{13} and not relaxation of E_{11} .

$^{\circ}\text{C}$	G_{13} , GPa	E_{11} , GPa	$P^{\text{Predicted}}$, N	$P^{\text{Experimental}}$, N
60	5.297	126.42	12.11	12.58
90	5.232	126.42	12.11	12.75
120	5.106	126.42	12.11	12.81
150	3.691	126.42	12.04	12.57
160	2.827	126.42	11.97	12.30
170	2.151	126.42	11.88	12.02
180	1.824	126.42	11.82	11.79
190	1.625	126.42	11.76	11.61
200	1.507	126.42	11.72	11.46
230	1.110	126.42	11.54	10.82
240	0.980	126.42	11.45	10.55
250	0.852	126.42	11.33	10.28
260	0.708	126.42	11.16	10.03
270	0.569	126.42	10.92	9.75
280	0.425	126.42	10.52	9.40
290	0.293	126.42	9.89	8.78
300	0.158	126.42	8.48	7.94

Table 2 Predicted and experimental central force, P for three-point bending of the 0-degree test geometry at temperatures ranging from 60 – 300 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for CF/PEKK composite

These results show that while the influence of temperature on deflection of the 0-degree beam would typically be expected to be due to a reduction of the Young's modulus, E_{11} , with temperature, the predictions of the force were carried out with equation (1) wherein E_{11} was held constant at 126.42 GPa. With temperature dependence of the shearing modulus, G_{13} utilized in the force predictions, good agreement between predicted force and observed force was demonstrated. This approach is counter to conventional interpretation of the use of the flexure test as a method to determine the temperature dependence of the Young's modulus. However, the general agreement between the predictions and experimental results demonstrate that when deflection is used as a measure of beam stiffness, there are two contributors to that stiffness and not one. Further, these results indicate that the major contributor to reduction in stiffness due to temperature in 0-degree flexure test is the shearing modulus, G_{13} and not E_{11} .

6 CONCLUSIONS

The first and primary conclusion of this work is that the 0-degree flexural test is inappropriate for the measurement of the time and temperature-dependent properties of the Young's modulus, E_{11} . Rather, this test yields data that reflects the time-dependent properties of the shearing modulus, G_{13} . Furthermore, extraction of G_{13} relaxation data from the 0-degree flexure sample test data, while plausible, is numerically difficult due to the form of equation (1) wherein G_{13} is in the denominator of the second term. This study also shows that the flexure test for the 90-degree fiber orientation geometry provides adequate data for the time dependent properties of the transvers Young's modulus, E_{22} so long as the beam aspect ratio, $L/h \geq 45$. Although the choice to derive the relaxation

data for the shearing modulus, G_{13} from that of the transverse Young's modulus, E_{22} is an approximation, it was shown to be useful in establishing the relationship between flexural deformation of the 0-degree sample and G_{13} , as witnessed by the agreement between predicted and observed relaxation force magnitudes. Finally, the difference between the tensile and compressive elastic modulus, E_{11} for the CF/PEKK materials system (139.0 GPa versus 127.0 GPa) was not considered in the present study, although results in reference [6] suggest the effect is of second order for CF/PEKK [1].

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